

DEVELOPMENT AND ACCEPTABILITY OF HYDROPONIC GARDEN

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the development and acceptability of hydroponic gardens as a viable alternative to traditional soil-based gardening, focusing on both circulating and non-circulating systems. Utilizing locally sourced materials, two hydroponic designs were created: one using PVC pipes and a submersible pump for nutrient circulation, and the other employing polyethylene and styrofoam for a non-circulating setup. Pechay seedlings were cultivated without soil, highlighting hydroponics' adaptability in urban settings with limited space. Evaluation by 20 faculty members, 10 hobbyists, 15 agriculture students, and 5 agriculturists confirmed the designs' functionality, economy, and instructional value. A Likert scale was used to assess the acceptability, showing high approval for both systems. The study concludes that hydroponics is an effective, innovative gardening method, particularly suitable for educational purposes and areas with space constraints. Further research is recommended to enhance the hydroponic designs, with a preference for non-circulating systems in educational settings.

Keywords: *Hydroponics, Circulating systems, Non-circulating systems, Urban gardening, Instructional value*

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the backbone of the Philippine economy, playing a critical role in food security, poverty alleviation, and rural development. It contributes significantly to employment-led economic growth through its various linkages and multiplier effects (Balisacan & Fuwa, 2004). However, the agricultural sector faces numerous challenges.

The population of the Philippines has been steadily increasing over the past decades, placing immense pressure on the agricultural resource base and necessitating a substantial increase in food production (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2020).

One of the critical issues facing agriculture in the Philippines is the fluctuation in vegetable prices, commonly referred to as "seasonal" changes, which are influenced by the economics of demand and supply. Inflation, driven by factors such as high oil prices, exacerbates this issue by increasing shipping costs, thereby raising the prices of vegetables over time (Briones & Dela Peña, 2014). Climate change also adversely affects vegetable production, leading to further volatility in prices (Lasco et al., 2016).

Data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020) revealed that in August of that year, the average prices of vegetables sold nationwide were 19.2% higher than the average prices from the previous year. This significant increase highlights the urgent need for sustainable and innovative solutions to address food security challenges.

In response to these challenges, the development and adoption of new agricultural technologies are imperative. The greatest challenge is to increase food production while maintaining ecosystem stability and rehabilitating the environment (Foley et al., 2011). The goal is to ensure that everyone is adequately and nutritiously fed without over-exploiting natural resources (Pretty et al., 2010).

The "*Gulayan sa Paaralan*" program, initiated by the Department of Education (DepEd) and aligned with the Department of Agriculture's goals, aims to enhance students' knowledge of the importance of growing plants and vegetables (Department of Education, 2018). This program emphasizes organic gardening technologies and the production of vegetables and fruits rich in proteins, vitamins, and minerals to improve children's nutrition (Francisco, 2017).

However, Patul National High School faces a significant challenge in implementing the "*Gulayan sa Paaralan*" program due to limited gardening space. The once fertile areas of soil on the campus are now covered with concrete, leaving little room for traditional gardening methods. Therefore, there is a pressing need to design and develop a hydroponic garden as a viable alternative.

Hydroponics offers a valuable means of growing fresh vegetables, fruits, and flowers, particularly in urban areas with shrinking land and water resources (Resh, 2012). It is defined as the cultivation of plants in a water and nutrient solution, eliminating the need for soil (Jensen, 1999). This method of soilless agriculture presents a high-tech solution for growing plants efficiently and sustainably.

Hydroponics provides several advantages, including the ability to control nutrient levels precisely, reuse water, and eliminate soil-borne pests and diseases (Savvas & Gruda, 2018). It is also environmentally friendly, as it reduces the release of pollutants into the environment (Barbosa et al., 2015). The potential to grow food in small spaces

and under various environmental conditions makes hydroponics an attractive option for urban farming (Despommier, 2010).

Moreover, hydroponic systems often utilize organic nutrients, aligning with the principles of organic farming (Owen, 2016). Urban farmers increasingly adopt hydroponics to grow food sustainably, recognizing the detrimental effects of excessive chemical fertilizers on soil fertility and groundwater (Foley et al., 2011).

Hydroponic gardening is particularly beneficial for areas with limited space, such as Patul National High School. It offers a reliable method of cultivation that results in high yields and reduces the risk of pests and diseases (Sharma et al., 2018). By integrating hydroponic systems into existing agricultural projects, schools and communities can produce sustainable food and enhance food security (Gruda, 2009).

This study aims to develop a hydroponic garden at Patul National High School to address the lack of soil space for the "*Gulayan sa Paaralan*" program. The research will explore the development and acceptability of hydroponic gardening as a sustainable solution to the challenges faced by schools and similar institutions.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and determine the acceptability of a hydroponic garden at Patul National High School, Santiago City, Philippines

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How are hydroponic gardens developed?
2. What is the level of acceptability of the two hydroponic gardens in terms of:
 - a. functionality
 - b. economy
 - c. workability
 - d. durability
 - e. safety
 - f. instructional capability
3. Is there a significant difference in the acceptability of hydroponic gardens as evaluated by:
 - a. faculty
 - b. hobbyist
 - c. students
 - d. agriculturist
4. Is there a significant difference in the acceptability of a circulating hydroponic garden and a non-circulating hydroponic garden?

METHODOLOGY

Project Design

The Hydroponic designs presented in this study had undergone steps of development. The project was developed and fabricated out of locally available parts and materials. One design for circulating hydroponics using GI pipes, PVC, and a submersible motor pump. Another design is for non-circulating hydroponics using recyclable materials. Both were used by the students and teachers in propagating *pechay* without the use of soil. The safety and comfort of the user were given emphasis.

A. Design of Circulating Hydroponics

PVC pipes with a 3-inch diameter were used, and a 25-watt submersible pump was connected to the PVC pipes using a rubber hose. The PVC pipes were drilled with ten holes in each pipe, connecting the PVC ends and couplings.

The water container, which had a capacity of 60 liters, was drilled, and the submersible pump was placed inside and connected to the hose. This setup allowed the water to flow up to the six PVC pipes and back into the water container. The water, combined with the SNAP solution, supplied the *pechay* seedlings with their needed nutrients and minerals.

Figure 1. Circulating Hydroponics with Submersible Motor Pump

B. Design of Non-Circulating Hydroponics

A styrobox of imported grapes and a polyethylene plastic bag (20"x30", 0.003mm thick) made of clear plastic were used in the non-circulating hydroponics design. Eight holes were made on the lid or cover of the box using a cutter. The plastic bag was used as a liner for the bottom half of the box to hold the nutrient solution. Packaging tape was used to close all the open slits of the lid or cover to prevent the entry of mosquitoes. The styrocup with slits was placed in the hole.

Figure 2. Non-Circulating Hydroponics

Project Development

The following are the materials and procedures in the fabrication of Circulating and Non-Circulating Hydroponics

A. Circulating Hydroponics

The circulating hydroponic used PVC pipes with a diameter of 3 inches, plastic cups (8oz), and 25 watts submersible pump for continuously applying the water with nutrients to the pipes. The use of 3" diameter PVC pipes made water efficiently flow thoroughly and made the pechay roots grow widely in the pipes.

Materials:

Equipment/Materials:

- 6 straight pipes of PVC (3 in diameter)
- 12 PVC ends with a 90* curve

- 15 PVC Coupling
- PVC glue (Solvent)
- Big tub
- Submersible water feature pump (25 TO 30W)
- 6 feet length of hose pipe
- Galvanized Iron pipe
- Vulcaseal
- Angle Bar
- plastic cups

Procedure:

To assemble the frame for your project, start by cutting the PVC pipes to the required lengths. Once the pipes are cut, glue the parts together securely. Afterward, drill the necessary plant holes into the PVC pipes, ensuring they are evenly spaced and properly aligned. Proceed to assemble the table-type frame by welding the steel parts together for added stability. Once the frame is sturdy, attach the PVC pipes to it. Next, connect the plastic hose to the PVC pipes using vulcaseal to ensure a watertight seal. Finally, paint both the pipes and the steel frame to protect them from the elements and enhance their appearance.

For the water container assembly, begin by drilling holes into the container as needed for the connections. Install the 25-watt submersible motor pump inside the container, making sure it is properly positioned and secured. Connect the water hose from the motor pump to the PVC pipes, ensuring a tight connection to facilitate smooth water flow through the system. With these steps completed, the assembly is ready for use.

B. Non-Circulating Hydroponics

The non-circulating hydroponic garden was made from polyethylene plastics, styrofoam boxes, and styrofoam cups. The use of polyethylene plastics with a thickness of 0.003mm made the project moss-free. The moss can absorb the nutrients from the water and there will be a competition in nutrients between pechay plants and moss.

Equipment /Materials needed:

- Styrofoam Box (boxes of imported grapes)
- Styrofoam cups (8 oz)
- 10 liters of water
- 25 ml of Nutrient Solution (SNAP Solution)
- Polyethylene plastic bag (20" x 30", 0.003mm thick)

Procedure:

To prepare your growing system, begin by making eight holes on the lid or cover of the box using a cutter. This will allow for the placement of your plants. Next, line the bottom half of the box with a plastic bag to ensure it can hold the nutrient solution without

leaking. Use packaging tape to seal all the open slits on the lid or cover to prevent mosquitoes from entering.

Place the styrofoam cups with slits into the holes you've cut on the lid. Then, position the boxes in a location where they can receive morning sunlight, making sure they are placed under a roof awning or transparent shed to prevent rainwater from entering the system. Arrange the growing boxes linearly on level ground or a bench, with the covers removed.

Fill each box with approximately 10 liters of tap water, and then add 25 ml of the nutrient solution to each box. Carefully place the seedling plugs into the holes on the lid or cover, ensuring that all cups are securely plugged into the holes. Finally, examine the boxes for any leaks and perform necessary troubleshooting to ensure the system is functioning properly.

Establishing the Seedlings

Materials Needed:

- Sowing/Seedling Tray
- Growing Media (Coco coir/peat)
- Pechay seeds
- Nutrient solution (SNAP Solution)

Procedure:

To begin the seedling process for pechay, start by filling a sowing or seedling tray with a layer of growing media, such as coco peat or coir, about an inch thick. Level the media to create an even surface. Scatter the pechay seeds uniformly and thinly across the media to ensure even germination. Water the seeds liberally every day, as you can expect germination to occur within 2 to 5 days.

Once the seeds have germinated, grow the seedlings under the sun for 7 to 14 days. This period allows the seedlings to strengthen and develop before transferring them to individual growing cups. When ready to transplant, dig a hole in the middle of the growing media in each cup and carefully place the pechay seedlings into the holes, ensuring they are securely positioned for optimal growth.

Testing Procedure

After constructing all the major components in their respective places, the project was subjected to a rigid test to determine its functionality.

1. Durability Test

- Breakage of Styrofoam
- Water capacity
- Structural design of steel frame

2. Functionality Test

- Pump is functional
- Safety from electrical shock

Table 1. Cost of Development

Item No.	QTY.		Unit	Specifications	Unit Price	Total Price
1	1		Assy.	Submersible motor pump	800	800
2	6		pc.	PVC Pipe 3”in diameter	150	900
3	4		pc.	G.I. Pipe (1x1 inch)	280	1,120
4	3		pc.	Angle Bar (1x1 inch.)	170	510
5	12		Pcs.	PVC Coupling	10	120
6	15		Pcs.	PVC Ends	15	225
7	1		pc	Solvent	150	150
8	1		set	Nutrient Solution	250	250
9	5		kilos	Coco Coir/Coco Peat	50	250
10	1		set	Polyethylene 20”x30” plastic	150	150
11	1		Pc.	Water container (60 liters)	280	280
12	5		m.	Rubber hose	35	175
13	1		Pc.	Vulcaseal	180	180
14	1		pc	Peachay seed	70	70
15	1		pc	Packaging Tape	25	25
16	80		Pcs.	Styro cups	1	80
17	60		Pcs.	Plastic Cups 8oz	1	60
Total Price						P5,345.00

The cost of supplies and materials in the development of (1) one unit of non-circulating hydroponics was Php. 125.00 while (1) one unit of Circulating hydroponics cost Php.4,710.00.

The cost of labor was estimated at 35% of the total cost of supplies and materials including the necessary procedures done in the production.

Table 2. Time consumed in the development of Circulating Hydroponics Design

Activities	Man Hours
1. Conceptualization	42 Hrs.
2. Preparation of Tools, Materials, and Parts	48 Hrs.
3. Fabrication of Parts	
3.1. Frame Assembly and PVC Drilling	36 Hrs.
3.2. Submersible Motor Pump System Assembly	5 Hrs.

4. Initial Testing	2 Hrs.
TOTAL	133 Hrs.

Table 3. Time Consumed in the Development of Non-Circulating Hydroponics Design

Activities	Man Hours
1. Conceptualization	4 Hrs.
2. Preparation of Tools, Materials, and Parts	48 Hrs.
3. Fabrication of Parts	
3.1 Cutting	12 Hrs.
3.2. Assembling of plastics and styrocups	5 Hrs.
4. Initial Testing	2 Hrs.
TOTAL	71 Hrs.

Evaluation Procedure

The evaluation was conducted through a survey, using the qualitative analysis method to determine the acceptability of the device. In the process, a survey on the functionality, economy, workability, durability, safety, and instructional applicability of the hydroponics design was solicited based on the format of the evaluation criteria for the hydroponics system. However, the study did not make use of all the criteria. Instead, it only used the ones related to the prototype to be used to keep a more concrete and definite outcome of evaluation. Each criterion is determined by a set of three indicators rated on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest.

The evaluation panel was composed of twenty (20) faculty members (Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers); ten (10), hobbyists, fifteen (15) agriculture students, and five (5) Agriculturists. These people were tapped because of their varying levels of expertise and experience in the field of Agriculture.

The results of the testing conducted were shown to the evaluators as evidence of the viability and reliability of hydroponics as a new, economical, and effective tool in gardening.

Demonstration on how the tool was operated was presented to all the members of the panel, thereafter, they were given an evaluation instrument to judge and evaluate the hydroponics system.

Treatment of Data

After the evaluation, the results were tabulated and interpreted. The Likert scale was employed to determine the equivalent descriptive rating of the weighted mean as shown below.

Weighted Mean	Descriptive equivalent
4.51 – 5.00	Highly Acceptable
3.51 – 4.50	Very Acceptable
2.51 – 3.50	Acceptable
1.51 – 2.50	Fairly Acceptable
1.00 – 1.50	Not Acceptable

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Project Description

A. Non-Circulating Hydroponics

The developed Non-Circulating hydroponics used Polyethylene plastic bag (20"x30", 0.003mm thick). Recycled Styrofoam fruit boxes were used as growing or culture pots where the nutrient solution was contained. The bottom part of the box was lined with a polyethylene sheet to prevent the nutrient solution from draining out. The lids of these boxes had prefabricated vents or openings that allowed the passive aeration of the roots.

B. Circulating Hydroponics

It is a hydroponic system where a continuous flow of nutrient solutions runs over the plant's roots. By using a 3" in diameter of PVC pipes the water was able to flow into six pipes vigorously. The system also used a 25-watt submersible pump to make the water with nutrient solution flow up to the rubber hose to the pipes and flow back to the water container.

Harvesting

After 32 days of observations, the growth of pechay in Non-circulating and circulating hydroponics were ready to harvest. In Non-circulating hydroponics harvested about (22) twenty-two kilograms of pechay, while Circulating hydroponics harvested (19) nineteen kilograms of pechay. The harvested pechay after cleaning, measuring, and bundling were sold to teachers, parents, and students. The total amount of the harvested pechay was Php.410.00.

Number of Yields

(Note: Each system contains 60 styrocups with pechay seedlings)

The table shows that the number of yields in non-circulating hydroponics is greater than in circulating hydroponics after 32 days (from germination to transplanting).

Table 4. Number of yields in Circulating and Non-Circulating Gardens after 32 Days

Hydroponics Garden	Number in kilograms
A.Non Circulating Hydroponics	22 kilograms
B. Circulating Hydroponics	19 kilograms

Product Evaluation

The Level of Acceptability of Circulating and Non-Circulating Hydroponic Gardens in terms of functionality, economy, workability, durability, safety, and instructional capability is shown in Table 2 below.

Table 5. Level of acceptability of circulating hydroponic garden per criterion

Criteria	Standard Deviation	Mean	Remark
Functionality	0.543	4.75	Highly Acceptable
Economy	0.632	4.60	Highly Acceptable
Workability	0.667	4.63	Highly Acceptable
Durability	0.616	4.68	Highly Acceptable
Safety	0.632	4.60	Highly Acceptable
Instructional Capability	0.362	4.85	Highly Acceptable
Grand Mean	0.575	4.68	Highly Acceptable

Table 5 reflects the level of acceptability of the Circulating Hydroponic Garden according to functionality, economy, workability, durability, safety, and instructional capability. It can be gleaned from the table that the project was rated "Highly Acceptable" by the respondents as to functionality, economy, workability, durability, safety, and instructional capability with means of 4.75, 4.60, 4.63, 4.68, and 4.85, respectively. Overall, the project is highly acceptable with a grand mean of 4.68.

The level of acceptability of circulating hydroponic gardens per criterion was highly acceptable for agriculturists, agriculture students, hobbyists, and Technology and Livelihood Teachers. However, the lowest mean was the economy and safety for circulating hydroponics which was the same as 4.60. Safety refers to the low probability of accident occurrence during operation.

The highest mean was the criteria under the instructional capability which has 4.85 with the same respondents. Instructional capability refers to the extent where the project supports the three domains of learning.

Table 6. Level of acceptability of non-circulating hydroponic garden per criterion

Criteria	Standard Deviation	Mean	Remark
Functionality	0.304	4.90	Highly Acceptable
Economy	0.335	4.87	Highly Acceptable
Workability	0.494	4.75	Highly Acceptable
Durability	0.385	4.82	Highly Acceptable
Safety	0.221	4.95	Highly Acceptable
Instructional Capability	0.267	4.93	Highly Acceptable
Grand Mean	0.334	4.87	Highly Acceptable

Table 6 shows the acceptability level of a Non-Circulating Hydroponic Garden in terms of functionality, economy, workability, durability, safety, and instructional capability. The respondents rated the project “Highly Acceptable” according to the criteria whose means are 4.90, 4.87, 4.75, 4.82, 4.95, and 4.93, respectively. The grand mean of 4.87 shows that overall, the project is “Highly Acceptable” among the respondents.

Comparison in the Level of Acceptability of Hydroponic Gardens among Faculty, Hobbyists, Students and Agriculturists

Table 7. Comparison of the level of acceptability of circulating hydroponic garden across varied groups.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	1.987	3	0.662	3.009	0.043
Within Groups	7.925	36	0.220		
Total	9.913	39			

Table 7 indicates the comparison of the level of general acceptability of non-circulating hydroponic gardens across varied groups. The means of the level of acceptability of the project significantly vary across the four (4) groups (F-test = 3.009, p-value < 0.05). This means that there is a significant difference in the level of acceptability of circulating hydroponic gardens among the varied groups.

Table 8. Multiple comparisons on the level of acceptability of circulating hydroponic gardens across varied groups.

(I) Evaluator	(J) Evaluator	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p-value	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Faculty	Hobbyists	-0.23300	0.25699	0.801	-0.9251	0.4591
	Students	-0.31133	0.24229	0.578	-0.9639	0.3412
	Agriculturists	0.23200	0.25699	0.803	-0.4601	0.9241
Hobbyists	Faculty	0.23300	0.25699	0.801	-0.4591	0.9251
	Students	-0.07833	0.19155	0.977	-0.5942	0.4376
	Agriculturists	0.46500	0.20983	0.138	-0.1001	1.0301
Students	Faculty	0.31133	0.24229	0.578	-0.3412	0.9639
	Hobbyists	0.07833	0.19155	0.977	-0.4376	0.5942
	Agriculturists	0.54333*	0.19155	0.036	0.0274	1.0592
Agriculturists	Faculty	-0.23200	0.25699	0.803	-0.9241	0.4601
	Hobbyists	-0.46500	0.20983	0.138	-1.0301	0.1001
	Students	-0.54333*	0.19155	0.036	-1.0592	-0.0274

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The table above shows multiple comparisons using Tukey HSD on the level of acceptability of circulating hydroponic gardens to determine where the difference lies among varied groups. It can be gleaned from the table that the level of acceptability of the project differed significantly between agriculturists and students as evidenced by a p-value of 0.036 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that agriculturists perceive the circulating hydroponic garden differently than students because of the former's educational background and expertise in Agriculture.

Table 9. Comparison of the level of acceptability of non-circulating hydroponic garden across varied groups.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	0.210	3	0.070	1.143	0.345
Within Groups	2.206	36	0.061		
Total	2.416	39			

Table 9 presents the comparison of the level of acceptability of non-circulating hydroponic gardens across varied groups. It can be gleaned from the table that there is

no significant difference in the level of acceptability of the project among the respondents as shown by an F-test value of 1.143, and a p-value (0.345) greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that the level of acceptability of non-circulating gardens is the same among varied groups.

Comparison of the Level of Acceptability of Circulating Hydroponic and Non-Circulating Hydroponic Gardens

Table 10. Comparison of the acceptability level of the two hydroponic gardens

T	Df	p-value	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
2.109	56.944	0.039	0.18750	0.08890	0.00948	0.36552

Table 10 presents the comparison of the General Level of Acceptability of Circulating and Non-Circulating Hydroponic Gardens. With $t = 2.109$; and a p-value (0.039) less than the 0.05 level of significance, a significant difference in the general acceptability levels of the two projects is established. This means that circulating and non-circulating hydroponic gardens differ significantly in the level of acceptability of the respondents. The circulating hydroponic has a grand mean of 4.68 and the non-circulating hydroponics garnered its grand mean of 4.87 showing that overall, the projects are “Highly Acceptable” among the respondents. With the mean difference of 0.18750, this means that non-circulating hydroponics is more highly acceptable than circulating hydroponics.

Conclusions

In light of the aforementioned findings, the study concludes that circulating and non-circulating hydroponics are highly accepted innovative ways of gardening. The developed hydroponic garden is functional, economical, workable, durable, safe, and has instructional value. It is very suitable in places with very limited area for planting like in highly urbanized areas. Developing a hydroponic garden (circulating and non-circulating) is easy as materials are readily available. Finally, yields or produce from hydroponic gardens are of high quality comparable to those produced from soil (garden).

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusion, the study forwards the following recommendations:

1. Hydroponics can be used as an instructional tool in school for introducing hydroponics gardening to students taking up vegetable production.
2. A hydroponic garden should be made as an alternative to a soil garden where the school has limited space for the *Gulayan sa Paaralan* program.

3. School managers may consider hydroponics as an innovation of gardening for the *Gulayan sa Paaralan* program.
4. Between the two types of hydroponic gardens, non-circulating hydroponics should be preferred for use in school.
5. Researchers can improve the design of circulating hydroponics and non-circulating hydroponics.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby assures that the study was conducted in strict adherence to research ethical standards, ensuring that participants provided informed consent, had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, their anonymity was preserved, their well-being was protected, no conflict of interest influenced the study, plagiarism was rigorously avoided, findings were interpreted without bias, and the results were used exclusively for research purposes.

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